

STATUS AND MARKETING PROSPECTS OF NAMANGAN PROVINCE ECOTOURS MARKET

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Abstract. *This article aims to identify ecotourism facilities in Namangan region, evaluate the current situation, show problems and give practical marketing suggestions for market development.*

Keywords: *ecotourism, ecological culture, marketing, tourist destination, agrotourism, ecotourism map.*

INTRODUCTION

In recent years, ecological tourism - ecotourism - has become one of the fastest growing tourism trends in the world. It serves to provide a person with a chance to relax in harmony with nature, improve their ecological culture, and ensure the well-being of the local population. Despite the great potential of ecotourism in Uzbekistan, in particular in the Namangan region, this trend has not yet been fully developed. This article analyzes the state of the ecotourism market in the Namangan region and studies its promising marketing directions.

The main objectives of the article are to identify ecotourism objects in the Namangan region, assess the current situation, identify problems, and provide practical marketing proposals for market development.

Data source. The data for this study were obtained by the author from the statistical collection of Namangan region (2020-2024), information on the tourism sector, the official websites of the Namangan region, the Tourism Committee under the Ministry of Ecology, Environmental Protection and Climate Change of the Republic of Uzbekistan, and the regional tourism department. Information on ecotourism culture and recreation parks of Namangan region was obtained from official website sources.

Literature Review. Tourism is a diverse phenomenon in which people travel to places or countries for a variety of people, topics, industries, activities, and behaviors. [1] In general, tourism-related attractions are considered as a factor that attracts tourists to visit a particular place or area, where the attractions should be well developed. [2] Thus, if there are no attractions, it is difficult to call a destination a tourism destination. A recent study found that an increasing number of people are looking for ways to explore authentic natural and cultural experiences [3]. Based on this fact, policymakers and researchers such as Destination Marketing Organizations (DMOs) have focused on the development of sustainable tourism. [4]. Previous studies have suggested that the development of sustainable ecotourism has several benefits, including poverty alleviation and the expansion of business opportunities.

The following scholars have conducted research on marketing processes in the field of ecotourism. In particular, Agula emphasizes the importance of infrastructure as a key factor in increasing the competitiveness of destinations in determining tourists' intentions to visit. [5] In addition, the importance of social media in the development of the sector, statistical analysis results have shown that the relationship between the use of social media marketing and the

competitiveness of the destination is negatively affected. [6] Domestic and international tourists visit so-called ecotourism or nature reserves to quickly escape from stressful work environments. However, destinations with convenient infrastructure and easy access lead to a potential increase in tourist arrivals. Thus, it is important to ensure that ecotourism destinations are of appropriate quality in order to maintain their competitiveness, comparative advantage and market position among competitors. [7],[8]. Furthermore, tourism infrastructure can be divided into two main categories, namely soft infrastructure, which includes visitor perceptions and experiences in tourist destinations. [9] Previous studies have proven the important role of key tourism resources and pull factors in developing the competitiveness of a tourist destination. [10] Tourism is a diverse phenomenon in which people, subjects, sectors, activities and behaviors travel to places or countries. In recent decades, tourism has begun to significantly affect local economies. [11], [12].

METHODOLOGY

To attract tourists, tourism marketing organizations allocate large budgets for advertising. Advertising messages can be conveyed through text, symbols, or images. Slogans are the most commonly used text form in marketing advertising [13]. Familiar brands have a better ability to capture information in consumers' memories than unfamiliar ones. [14]

Main part. Namangan region is a region rich in natural beauty and biodiversity. Mountainous places such as Chodak, Govasoy, Nanay, rivers, lakes and forests in the region create a sufficient basis for the development of ecotourism. The natural landscapes, clean air and peaceful environment in these areas allow for ecological recreation.

In Namangan region, agrotourism combined with agriculture, cultural tourism associated with valley traditions can also be developed along with ecotourism. The hospitality of the local population and rich traditional cuisine are also attractive features for tourists.

Current state of the ecotourism market. In recent years, the Namangan region has seen an increase in tourist flows, but most of them still prefer traditional resorts. The number of tour operators specializing in ecotourism is limited, and those that exist are mainly aimed at domestic tourists. The current state of the ecotourism market in the region is presented below:

Table 1.

Objects of large ecotourism culture and recreation parks of Namangan region (Author's development based on the official websites of the objects)

№	The name of the ecotourism object	characteristic
1.	A park named after Babur	The park covers an area of 1 hectare, has 1.5 km of irrigation networks and 1 modern fountain. An open-air stage and an amphitheater for 400 spectators have been built on the park's territory. 175 seats and 160 night lights have been installed for residents to relax in the area.
2.	Chust Culture and Recreation Park	The territory of the park is 6.1 hectares. It has a 5-century history and is visited by up to 4,000 eco-tourists during the season.
3.	New Uzbekistan Park	The garden area covers an area of 68 hectares, trees and flowers are maintained

		in a different district, with a modern landscape.
4.	Valley of Legends Theme Park	The park covers an area of 155 hectares and has the largest Ferris wheel in Uzbekistan. The park has 10 service and 5 technical buildings, 16 swimming pools and an indoor and outdoor water park with 7 different water attractions.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The infrastructure, i.e. roads, accommodation, catering facilities and sanitation, does not meet the requirements specific to ecotourism. The lack of service facilities around nature reserves and national parks reduces the interest of tourists. In addition, due to the insufficient level of environmental education of the population, the connection between tourism and nature conservation is not sufficiently promoted. This creates obstacles to ecotourism activities.

Problems in the field of ecotourism in the region. The following are the main problems in the development of ecotourism:

Low level of infrastructure - including roads, toilets, water supply and electricity networks are not well established. Lack of specially trained personnel - there are not enough guides, ecologists, service workers and marketers in the field. Insufficient promotion of marketing and advertising activities - many natural objects in the region are not advertised on the Internet, and there are not enough maps of routes.

Figure 1. Mechanism of ecotourism marketing prospects in Namangan region (Author development)

Strategic directions for the development of the sector may include:

-identifying the target audience - domestic and foreign nature-loving tourists, photojournalists, researchers.

-diversifying tour products - organizing hiking, agrotours, ecocamps, cycling tours in mountainous areas.

-improving legislation - adopting regulatory documents that combine nature protection and tourism.

Tactical measures

-digital marketing - strengthening the promotion of the region through Instagram, YouTube, Google Maps and TripAdvisor.

-branding - creating local brands such as “Namangan EcoTour” or “Chodak Green Life”.

-festivals and events - raising public awareness through ecotourism week, “EcoDay Namangan” campaigns.

-education and training - organizing training courses for local residents in the field of guiding and service.

Table 2.

Territorial branding opportunities of Namangan region (Author development)

№	Territory name	A brand or tagline	Tourist opportunities of the region
1.	Chartak district	"Healthy Life Mineral Waters", Land of Healing Springs	Name of the object: "Sultan Uwais Qaroniy" shrine, tourist destination name: ecotourism (mountainous area and riverside tourist attractions).
2.	Chust district	The knife of the heart is not in the hand, but in the heart.	Name of the organization: Buonamozor” and “Ayritom Bobo”, G’ova, “Bibiona” pilgrimage site, name of the tourist destination: gastronomic tourism (Chust osh markazi, mega pilaf),
3.	Kosonsoy	Land of milky rivers	Name of the unit: Almazar neighborhoods Name of the tourist destination: ecotourism (mountainous area and riverside tourist attractions),
5.	Mingbulak	The green space is huge	Name of the place: Batyr Botka, Gulbog, Mehnatabad Tourist destination name: Ecotourism (melon walk).
6.	Namangan city	City of flowers	Name of the company: "On Bir Ahmad" and "Kadir Khoja Eshon Uy" Name of the tourist destination: ecotourism, pilgrimage tourism
7.	Namangan district	Riverbank	name of the organization: "Khilvatkhona" pilgrimage sites name of the tourist destination: agrotourism, ethnotourism

9.	Naryn district	the mist that lives in the luster of the waters	Name of the place: Bulakli Mausoleum, Bori Tapa Name of the tourist destination: historical
12.	Pop district	Way to space! A sunny corner on the mountainside. A golden bridge connecting the valley and the capital	Name of the place: Chodak, "Hazrati Bob" pilgrimage site Name of the tourist destination: ecotourism (mountainous area and riverside tourist attractions).
14.	Turakurgon district	The old history is gone When history speaks, Turakurgon speaks	tourist attraction name: "Akhsikent Open Sky Museum", tourist destination name: historical, eco-agrotourism
16.	Uchkurgan district	Eat your fill of fish! Live long!	name of the tourist destination: ecotourism (fishing)
18.	Uychi	City of Seven Treasures	Name of the place:: "Devona buva", Dehqanabad village
20.	Yangikurgon	Uzbekistan Switzerland	name of the region: Nanay, tourist destination name: ecotourism (mountainous area and riverside tourist attractions).

COCNCLUSION

In conclusion, the natural resources of the Namangan region, the favorable environment for ecotourism, and the hospitality of the local population show great potential in this direction. However, for successful development, a systematic approach, infrastructure improvement, personnel training, and effective marketing strategies are necessary, and we recommend the following:

- a regional ecotourism development strategy should be developed.
- an ecotourism map and routes should be developed for each district.
- investment projects should be implemented in partnership with the private sector and the state.
- a balance between tourism and nature protection should be ensured.

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